

THE IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL NETWORKS IN SPEAKING

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Abstract. *This paper work aims to show how to use the internet in daily connect ways or learning skills in English . There are given majority of examples that learners come across any type of problems . many individuals tend to online speech than others . Online and social networkings has recently gaining ground across the globe for variety of reasons . Not only how to speak fluently but also positive cognitive abilities .*

Keywords . *Teaching and learning skills and social networks , fetchingly accent , non – related thoughts , communicate online, attraction accent , bad effects , elaborateness ways to speech fluently.*

Introduction .

Internet is one of the greatest tool we have today billons information unlimited way to connect games to play , videos to watch things to learn . There is the same thing for every one . Social networking is connecting incredibly way . You may use the social networking not only fluently speech but also learning new tips and how to pronunciation correctly . Technically ,right accent.

Social media has just amplified this, as it's right in the users 's faces when they open a social media app. Moreover we can find a various reasons to use online social media and new types of apps for increasingly speaking fluently . As soon as Instagram is opened , for example , there is an endless feed of what looks like the perfect life . From personal accomplishments , lavish vacations , expensive designer clothes and special apps for learning English . The social media can develop their common problem because many language learners only complaint from this type of some apps the reason why any social media apps have a lot of advert isements . There are many sorts of speech in the internet not only live speech but also crucial managing life experiences . It is true that children can learn some kind of foreign language not only their speech but also important pronunciations. Subsequently , some secondary school children tend to more special and interesting language activities in the social networking system and their parents do not permit all the time which is using always social media as a result of some teens do not other type of language games not only games but also they do not know some kind of useful apps . Nowadays , many students should know about some useful learning speech apps and this kind of role can attend other their career . If students or pupils will know about some kind of social media apps or crucial sites , they can understand how to learning language and also know their language mother tongue . Eventually , children also do not have any hesitations while learning ; they are not afraid that others will laugh at them if they speak wrongly . In addition , there any of advantage learning language from social networking on account of , their psychologists often mention that the most formative years of learning happen in the first few years . Therefore , what children are exposed to is very often retained and remembered . In this way , a child is in a good position to learn the new information associated with new language .

In some social network employers want to widespread their networking system . In addition , social media can be an extremely valuable platform for a wide variety of uses , but it can also be very dangerous if used incorrectly . Throughout the years can open some type of

networking faces. With all the different types of social media is an excellent opportunity for your study not only studying on institute or school but also improve your informational database . In fact , in 2022 , sales on social media reached an estimated value of 922 billion . But before you start learning, you must learn grammatical language. Here benefits of social networks in speaking you can use then your speech . .

1.Enhanced communication . Social networks provide a platform for real-time communication.

2. Cultural exchange . Users can engage in conversation with people and learn words how to pronunciation.

3.Knowledge sharing . Some platforms facilitate the exchange of ideas , information and , expertise contributing to continuous learning and personal development . Especially students need to communicate usually with each others 4. Language practice . Social networks provide opportunities for language learners to practice and improve their through interactions with native speakers .

5.Increase accessibility to information . Users gain quick access to news , trends , and updates staying informed about local global events . Even though , mostly public speaking opportunities platforms like LinkedIn or You tube enable users to share their ideas with a broader audience , honing their public speaking . Therefore , social networking plays a crucial role in improving speaking skills by providing platform for communication , language exposure , and opportunities for real-time language practice .One of the main idea around the social media networking access to information and creativity. Furthermore , many students tend to learn online social networking courses because of some reasons such as remotely education and saving money efficiently education . It is often seen that some students say about networking with their learn new language speech is became more and more useful crucial because , if they learn new language of speech , they will be gifted students in every area . Some intelligent students do not except any negative differ of social networking because they know hoe to improve their speech faster, clear and fluent . However , some effective measures can be taken address or least reduce the some serious problem . If networking does not work some students begin to complain about it , of course networks is not working stabilize but some advantages are not without disadvantages. Even thought many benefits pros than cons . Social media helped students to reduce their speaking anxiety , gain confidence in speaking and at the same time become more motivated to use the language . People excepted some of bad intend through internet but if they want to except some useful apps for learning language speech they will lost poor pronunciation and some garbage voice . One of the benefits of using social media for public speaking is that you can practice and feedback from your online community .

Every day you must give to yourself . How I can improve my speaking pronunciation . The use of acronyms an abbreviation formed from the initial letters of other words and pronounced as a word .

The diverse nature of social networks exposes individuals to various communication styles and cultural nuances contributing to a well – rounded and adaptable speaking proficiency . It is beneficial of social networks.

CONCLUSION.

The conclusion of a speech on social networking could emphasize the dual nature of its impact – highlighting the positive aspects like connectivity and information sharing , while

cautioning against the potential pitfalls such as privacy concerns and online toxicity. There are many benefits of social networking it will also become increasingly common day by day.

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